

IPBES VA Chapter 3 Analysis of Contributions on Values and Valuation Methods by ILK experts and holders

Code: VA_3.6_Ch3

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Description: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment. The methodology explained in this report responds to the mandate of Ch. 3 that will assess different valuation methodologies and approaches, including (a) biophysical, social and cultural, economic, health and holistic (including indigenous and local community-based) and (b) approaches to the integration and bridging of different types of values. Information concerning the methods, values and approaches used by the Indigenous People and Local Communities has been found to be scattered and scarce, to be able to solve this void of information we identified a set of potential Contributing Authors, that delivered targeted contributions describing the values and valuation methods used by different communities across the globe. We analysed these contributions using Qualitative Analysis tools. The results will be used to nourish different sections of the chapter.

Process overview:

miro

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Qualitative Analysis of ILK Contributions

Contribution languages: English, Spanish

Search engine: Google, Google Scholar, ILK Taskforce suggestions, Author suggestions (to identify Contributing Authors)

Exact Search Date for potential contributors: February 1st - May 30 2020

Fields extracted (A):

- Region
- Name of potential CA
- Institutional Affiliation
- Email address
- Links to work
- Expertise (country, communities or livelihoods of expertise)

Location and Format of the Data (A): IPBES VA_3.6_Authors invited_A.csv

Sample of confirmed contributors (B): 31 contributing authors.

Location and Format of the Data (B): IPBES VA_3.6_Contributing Authors_(B).csv

Treatment applied (R1): IPBES VA_3.6_Guiding Questions_(R1).pdf (set of guiding questions used to support the development of experts contributions).

Sample extracted (contributions received) (C): 26 contributions were received following FPIC principles.

Location and Format of the Data (C): IPBES VA_3.6_Supplementary Material_(C).pdf

Treatment applied (R2): Each contribution was assessed and coded qualitatively using (R2): IPBES VA_3.6_Code_ILK_Analysis_(R2).csv The contributions were coded using Dedoose Software to ensure easy extraction of primary data afterwards. This analysis led to a roster of codes and their associated excerpts.

Sample extracted (D): 1240 excerpts.

Location and Format of the Data (D): IPBES

VA_3.6_ILK_CAs_Excerpts_2020_10_27_1651_(D).csv

Analysis of the data: The resulting excerpts and the full contributions, were analyzed and summarized to present a general view of the methodologies used by the IPLC's, the results are presented in Section 3.2.4 Valuation Practice in IPLC contexts; across Chapter 3 and in the Annexes.

Documents attached:

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	IPBES VA_3.6_Authors invited_(A)	.csv	18 KB	List of potential contributing authors
B	IPBES VA_3.6_Contributing Authors_(B)	.csv	5 KB	List of 31 contributing authors that accepted the invitation and sent their contributions.
C	IPBES VA_3.6_Supplementary Material_(C)	.pdf	4.5 MB	Document that presents the 26 contributions that were received.
D	IPBES VA_3.6_ILK_CAs_Excerpts_2020_10_27_1651_(D)	.csv	1.4 MB	List of excerpts obtained after using the code presented in (R2) (1240 excerpts).
R1	IPBES VA_3.6_Guiding Questions_(R1)	.pdf	124 KB	Set of questions sent to the contributing authors to guide the content of the contributions towards valuation methods used by IPLC's.
R2	IPBES VA_3.6_Code_ILK_Analysis_(R2)	.csv	16 KB	Criteria used to code the

				26 contributions received, and their description.
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